

THE BENEFITS OF GYMNASTICS FOR HUMAN HEALTH

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Abstract: physical education reached a particular level of interest and importance in our country. It is taught from the primary education to the finish of all studies. By the bright attendance and presence of our athletes in the world arenas, the sound of the name of our country getting louder and obtaining the worldwide attention. However, it does not mean we conquered the world stage by representation of our athletes in all sport types. Only few of them is under big observation. The sport type that is having troubles to breakthrough is gymnastics. The following article discusses some issues related to that topic and shares possible solutions.

Keywords: women's sports, physical, education, training, gymnastics, apparatus, shell, competition, republican, specialists.

In general, the problem of young men and women's sports is taken seriously: in our country, new laws are being adopted and numerous studies are being carried out in which more modern methods of developing physical abilities are being developed, but gymnastics is not developing at the same time. For a long time, we have not seen our gymnasts (except for Oksana Chusovitina) on the podium in world championships, crowds of boys competing on a horizontal bar in the yard, girls stopped jumping rope and spinning hoops. Such standards as jumping over a horse and combinations on uneven bars disappeared among applicants entering the Faculty of Physical Education [1]. Have forgotten what gymnastic holidays and mass performances of gymnasts are. We all know perfectly well that gymnastics is a very spectacular sport, gymnastic exercises are basic and indispensable in physical training in many sports, and develops all physical qualities. There are such types of gymnastics as health-improving, medical, industrial, professional-applied, athletic, etc. And here the actual problems of the lack of qualified specialists. As a result, logical questions arise: How to revive the former popularity of this sport? How to train specialists of this field?

Analyzing the above, it is necessary to start working with preschool institutions. Because the base, the foundation of development begins at this age. Gymnastics instructors should be involved in kindergartens, they will put the correct posture with the help of gymnastic exercises, improve health, develop flexibility (splits, bridges, folds) and teach minimal basic exercises. And most importantly, they will find the most gifted children for the gymnastics section. In the Ministry of Public Education, it is necessary to increase the number of schools in which gyms will be equipped to a greater extent with gymnastic apparatus and physical education teachers would have gymnastics categories, where schoolchildren would have the opportunity to learn via all devices during the lesson. Open gymnastics sections on the basis of the school, where teachers, after their major hours, could conduct classes among students who wanted to, so that the teacher's work was paid. Organize at least 2 competitions a year

between schools according to a lightweight program for 3-4 gymnastic apparatus for boys, 2-3 gymnastic apparatus for girls [2]. On sports grounds, you need to build such shells from durable metal as horizontal bars of different heights, parallel bars, wall bars, iron ropes, press fixtures, semi-exercise equipment, etc. Conduct systematically seminars in which teachers exchange experience among colleagues. Naturally, it is necessary in every possible way to encourage financially the most distinguished teachers.

There is a shortage of female teachers in universities. This is especially true among women's sports groups. A small example: in a gymnastics class, a male teacher with our mentality in practical classes cannot, while teaching this or that element, support, pick up, insure female students, etc., when, as among male students, there are no problems with this, especially between the teacher and female students should have close communication, to which not every female student will open up to a male teacher. And in universities there is a sorely lack of high-quality gymnastic equipment, sports grounds are not equipped for outdoor gymnastics in warm weather, but they could be used, including by students from other faculties, thereby developing mass gymnastics. It's probably time to include artistic and rhythmic gymnastics competitions in the Universiad program. To begin with, you can conduct competitions in a lightweight form: it may look something like this: men compete in 3-4 shells out of 6, and women in 2-3 out of 4. In each semester, you need to organize the same competition between groups, based on the results of which you can select the best. A festive competitive environment will positively influence students, motivating them to achieve great results. Of course, all this requires some work and a topic for discussion [3].

And you should also pay attention to the knowledge of the foreign language among athletes. Probably, it would be better to take tests or dictation when accepting documents from an applicant who is going to enter the certain groups. After all, it's not a secret for anyone when our athletes go to competitions in neighboring countries, in neighboring republics there, and coaches, judges, organizers, almost all communicate mostly in Russian. Even here, at major Republican competitions, teams and sports terms are voiced in Russian and English..

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